

Product User Manual for the RFC C++ Implementation to be used for TROPOMI CH4

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document number : SRON-S5P-LEV2-RP-002
CI identification : CI-7430-PUM
issue : 1.0.0
date : 2024-11-27
status : released

Document approval record

	digital signature
prepared:	
checked:	
approved PM:	
approved PI:	

Document change record

issue	date	item	comments
1.0.0	2024-11-27	All	Initial draft version

Contents

Document approval record	2
Document change record	3
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Identification	5
1.2 Purpose and objectives	5
1.3 Document overview	5
2 List of abbreviations	6
3 Installing the Software	7
3.1 Overview	7
3.2 Prerequisites	7
3.3 Installation Steps	7
4 Interface definition	8
5 Usage of the Software	9
5.1 Overview	9
5.2 Using Balsa from C++	9
5.3 Compiling and Linking	9
6 File Formats	11

1 Introduction

1.1 Identification

This document outlines the usage of the Random Forest Classifier (RFC) Implementation in C++, tailored for cloud clearing of Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) CH₄ data to be integrated into the operational processing pipeline of the European Space Agency (ESA). The RFC implementation serves as a pivotal component aimed at refining TROPOMI XCH₄ measurements by effectively filtering out cloud-contaminated scenes.

1.2 Purpose and objectives

The purpose of this document is to familiarize users with the installation process, usage guidelines, and interface definitions of the software library, along with clarifying input-output conventions. Additionally, we elucidate the utilization of the three RFC classifiers trained on TROPOMI data, designed to replicate cloud clearing based on cloud fractions of 0.1, 0.02, and 0.001.

1.3 Document overview

The document is organized as follows: Following this introduction, Section 2 provides a list of abbreviations used throughout the document, followed by installation instructions in Sec. 3. Sec. 4 defines the interfaces of the software packages for the implementation in ESA's operational processing chain. The installation and usage of the software package are outlined in Sec. 5. Sec. 6 gives the file conventions.

2 List of abbreviations

Acronyms

ESA European Space Agency.

RFC Random Forest Classifier.

TROPOMI Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument.

3 Installing the Software

3.1 Overview

This section provides a summarized reproduction of the standard installation procedure of Balsa, the optimized C++ implementation of the RFC algorithm. These instructions cover the installation of Balsa in the default location on a UNIX system. The full installation instructions (including Windows-specifics) can be found in the Balsa documentation, in the file “Documentations/BalsaManual.md” of the Balsa source tree.

The Balsa package consists of a C++ library that can be embedded in a third-party C++ application, and a set of stand-alone command-line tools that can be used to train Random Forest models and/or use them for classification of data points. In the default installation procedure, both the C++ library and the command-line tools are installed on the target system.

3.2 Prerequisites

To install Balsa on a target system, the following requirements must be satisfied:

- A C++ compiler that is compliant to the C++17 standard or a later standard.
- The CMake build system, version 3.5.0 or later.
- A local copy of the Balsa package source code.

The prerequisites will be checked automatically during the Balsa build process on the target system.

3.3 Installation Steps

1. Open a shell and navigate to the top-level directory of the local copy of the Balsa source tree.
2. Create a temporary ‘build’ directory using `mkdir build`, and navigate into it using `cd build`.
3. From the build directory, invoke CMake on the top-level directory to generate build files using the command `cmake ..`. If errors occur during this step, the target system is not configured properly. Please review the errors and the installation prerequisites.
4. Build the software using the command `make`.
5. Install the software by issuing the command `make install`.

4 Interface definition

The Balsa interface for classification consists of a single C++ class template that has to be instantiated with the name of a model file as a parameter. The instantiated classifier object can be used repeatedly to classify batches of data points.

In order to perform classification, the caller provides a buffer that contains the point data. The point data consists of a sequence of floating-point values. For a data set of n features, each point consists of n feature values in the input buffer. The caller also provides an output buffer for the label values. Labels are integers of type `balsa::Label`.

Section 5 provides a complete example that demonstrates how Balsa's Random Forest classifier object is instantiated and used. Additional examples can be found in the full Balsa manual.

5 Usage of the Software

5.1 Overview

This section shows the basic scenario of using Balsa from within a third-party C++ application from the Balsa manual. This summary only covers model-loading and classification. The full manual is distributed in the Balsa source code package, in the Markdown file "Documentation/BalsaManual.md". It covers usage of the stand-alone command-line tools, using Balsa for model training, and other functionality. For access to the source code, please visit the repository at: <https://github.com/borsdorff/Balsa>.

5.2 Using Balsa from C++

Balsa can be included in a C++ project by including the header file "balsa.h" from a system-wide standard location (i.e. using angle-brackets). To use Balsa for classification, the caller must construct a RandomForestClassifier object with a reference to the path of the trained Random Forest model file.

The following minimal example demonstrates how Balsa can be used to classify data points that are located in a C++ vector:

```
#include <balsa.h>

const unsigned int FEATURES_PER_POINT = 7;
const unsigned int POINT_COUNT = 100;

int main ( int, char ** )
{
    // Define a container for input data (points).
    // The container may be any type, as long as it is randomly
    // accessible through an iterator. The element data type
    // must be either float or double. Each point consists of
    // a number of feature values. Points are stored in row-
    // major order.
    typedef std::vector<double> Points;
    Points points( FEATURES_PER_POINT * POINT_COUNT );

    // ... fill in the point data ...

    // Define a container for the output data (labels).
    // The container must provide pre-allocated space for all
    // the point labels. The container must be random-access
    // iterable. The labels may be any integer type.
    typedef std::vector<balsa::Label> Labels;
    Labels labels( POINT_COUNT );

    // Create a Random Forest classifier for the chosen input-
    // and output-container types.
    RandomForestClassifier classifier( "forest-model.balsa" );

    // Classify the points in bulk.
    classifier.classify( points.begin(), points.end(), labels.begin() );

    // ... use the label values ...
}
```

As indicated in the comments, the caller has considerable flexibility in choosing the C++ containers in which input is provided and output is collected.

5.3 Compiling and Linking

An application that is based on Balsa must link against the installed Balsa shared library during the build process. Additionally, the compiler must be instructed to use an appropriately advanced C++ standard (C++17 or later). On a UNIX-based system, a typical command-line invocation might look like this:

```
++ -std=c++17 example.cpp -lbalsa -o example
```

6 File Formats

Balsa uses an opaque binary file format for storing trained models. This file format is optimized for fast model loading and sparse memory usage. By intention, the file format is not part of the public interface of Balsa. By keeping the format closed, it is possible for future versions of Balsa to further optimize performance, without breaking third-party client code.